

Wind Tunnel Experiments of Long Arcs in Crossflow

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Abstract— Lightning attachment to aircraft follows a series of distinct phases occurring at disparate timescales. Whereas the stages of leader inception and initial attachment are fast compared to the fluid timescales, once the bidirectional discharge is established, the current flow phase can last on the order of a second: including, current pulses of amplitude $\sim 1\text{kA}$ associated with the stepped propagation of the negative leader, a steady current component (of a few hundred A) and a series of intracloud, cloud-to-ground or cloud-to-cloud process pulses ($< 100\text{kA}$). During this time, which corresponds to the most damaging phases of the arc, the aircraft can travel several times its length. At the local level, this swept stroke phase involves the complex interaction between a long arc and a fluid boundary layer. Improved understanding of this local problem can lead to revised modelling approaches of the swept stroke phase.

In this contribution we perform wind tunnel experiments of a long arc in cross flow and perform synchronized diagnostics of both the fluid dynamics and the arc dynamics, as a first step to tackling the local problem of lightning attachment associated with the swept stroke. Although the swept stroke phase is most closely represented by a moving electrode setup (the arc column is stagnant with respect to the ambient air and the segment attached to the surface experiences the relative velocity), wind tunnel tests can be useful to isolate the effects of different flow fields on the arc dynamics, as the environment can be easily controlled. In this joint effort between the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, and ONERA, we have initiated wind tunnel studies of long arcs, starting from an arc column of length around 20-80cm and currents of $\sim 3\text{A}$. The experimental setup is equipped to diagnose both the arc properties and the fluid flow. The arc is characterized by its electrical signature (time-resolved current and voltage waveforms) as well as high-speed videography to resolve the elongation of the arc in response to the flow and possible reconnection and reattachment events. The fluid flow field is visualized in 2D using particle image velocimetry (PIV). This setup allows to isolate the influence of the flow dynamics (laminar versus turbulent, separation, etc.) on the arc dynamics.

Keywords— lightning attachment, swept stroke, wind tunnel, particle image velocimetry (PIV), lightning zoning, long arc in crossflow

I. INTRODUCTION

Laboratory tests to model the swept stroke include wind tunnel tests and moving surface experiments. A comprehensive summary of experiments simulating the swept stroke is given by Plumer [1], much of this work was done between 1965-1980. For the wind tunnel approach, both electrodes (a far field electrode, and the test specimen representing the aircraft) are stationary, and wind from a wind tunnel is used to blow the arc along the surface. Much of the prior work using wind tunnel tests has focused on complex specimens, mostly scale models of different vehicles, and did not target time and spatially resolved characterization of the arc dynamics and the flow. An example is the work in Ref. [2] using a 0.03 scale model of the Space Shuttle and 4-6m long arcs. The diagnostics included high speed and still photography. The advantage of this setup is that it allows greater control of the flow field characteristics and a more compact setup for characterization. Depending on the electrode arrangement, the arc will be dynamically constrained by one of the electrodes and swept over the other one or be left to freely move along both. The drawback of this configuration is that the arc is affected by the airflow along the entirety of its length, which will affect its cooling properties and therefore the constriction of the arc. In reality, the lightning channel is stationary in air and only the segment near the aircraft surface is affected by the relative velocity. Moving surface tests avoid this artifact. In a moving electrode setup, the test specimen is moved relative to the arc leading to a more realistic simulation. Experiments in the literature include placing the test surface on top of a truck (reaching speeds $\sim 15\text{m/s}$) [1], propelling the test surface along a rail

track by releasing a stretched elastic band (able to access speeds $\sim 20\text{m/s}$), or using a wing mounted on a rocket sled (which can access velocities of $\sim 72\text{m/s}$) [3]. From these efforts, the last one is the most interesting due to the higher velocity achieved. The experiment with the rocket sled considered an electrode spacing of 20cm, leading to arc lengths around 5m, with arc current of 600A. The surface properties of the wing were varied (painted and unpainted aluminium, CFRP with and without aluminium foil) and the fluid boundary layer thickness was modified by using spoilers. Diagnostics used included current and voltage waveforms as well as video camera recording at 12,000fps from which the arc dwell time and skip distance could be obtained. More recently, Andraud et al. [4,5] experimentally studied the swept stroke using an electromagnetic launcher propelling aeronautical samples, and reached speeds around 80m/s. The current conditions were that of the swept stroke C phase, using the ONERA lightning current generator (GRIFON), which is able to sustain 400A for a few hundreds of ms. These experiments have revealed interesting behaviours comparing anodic and cathodic arc root dynamics, in a very relevant environment, using electrical measurements and high-speed imaging. However, the complexity of the setup combined with the lack of fluid-specific diagnostics did not allow the evaluation on the impact of the flow dynamics on the arc column and arc root behaviour.

This work aims to complement those experiments in two ways. First, a wind tunnel experiment with low current arcs (around 3A DC) is conducted to identify the relevance of simpler experimental conditions to the aircraft swept stroke problem. Second, diagnostics are enhanced to visualize the fluid flow field and quantitatively assess the influence of the fluid dynamics on the arc column and arc root dynamics. The fluid flow is visualized using particle image velocimetry (PIV), a standard technique in experimental fluid physics, which allows to obtain the fluid flow velocity field in 2D. The near-wall behaviour of the flow is controlled by using as a test specimen an airfoil with variable angle of attack (AOA) and wind tunnel flows at various wind speeds. At low AOA and low wind speed, the flow is laminar and remains attached to the surface. At high AOA, the flow separates and introduces a separation region of low velocity and high turbulence that will impact the arc root dynamics [6]. This contribution experimentally explores the two-way coupling between the fluid dynamics and the arc-root dynamics.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

An experimental campaign was conducted in April 2024 in a collaborative effort between the *Aerospace Plasma Group* at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), the *Lightning Research Group* at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), and the *Lightning, Plasmas and Application* research group at the French Aerospace Research Center (ONERA). This section overviews the experimental facility that was constructed for this purpose.

A. Wind Tunnel Experimental Setup

All experiments were conducted in an open section wind tunnel available in the Aeronautics and Astronautics Department at MIT. The tunnel has an exit square cross section of 45.7cm x 45.7cm and can reach wind speeds of 30m/s. At the exit of the wind tunnel, a 61cm long acrylic test section is appended. One of the side panels and the top panel are left transparent for optical access for both the laser sheet diagnostics (coming from the top) and the camera detector visualization (from the side). The other two panels are covered with black adhesive to minimize reflections. In the middle of the test section, a NACA 0012 airfoil with 30cm chord is mounted, attached to a rod which is slotted into the acrylic frame. The airfoil can be positioned at a variable angle of attack from 0 to 20 degrees.

The airfoil serves as one of the electrodes: a 1cm wide strip of stainless-steel foil is adhered to the midpoint of the airfoil, along the streamwise direction, and the rest is covered with black tape. Upstream of the airfoil's leading edge, at 4cm from it, an aluminium spherical electrode of radius 1.25cm is placed to allow igniting the arc ahead of the sample. These two electrodes are electrically connected and set to the same voltage. The opposite polarity electrode is inserted from the top of the test section, and vertically aligned with the ball electrode, and consists of a second ball electrode (made of stainless steel) of radius 0.7cm mounted on a pneumatic system to allow for remote control of its motion. This electrode can be lowered and retracted at variable speed and is used to ignite the electrical arc by short circuit. The inter-electrode gap between the ball electrodes (top electrode fully retracted) is 12.7cm. For some of the experiments, an additional rail electrode was mounted at the top panel of the acrylic test section, aligned with the strip electrode on the airfoil. This rail electrode, made of stainless steel, consists of a bracket of 0.1cm thickness and 10cm height that is electrically connected to the retractable electrode and allows the upper arc root to be swept. This contrasts with the ball electrode alone which tends to constrain the motion of the upper arc root and lock it in place.

B. High Voltage DC Generator

Fig. 1 Electric schematic of the high voltage DC generator including the high voltage and current probes.

A 5.4kV/6A three-phase full-bridge rectifier generator generated the arcs in the described electrode system. To accommodate the generator in the limited electric power and space of the wind tunnel laboratory, a three-phase resonant

transformer was used to supply the rectified high-voltage (Fig. 1). The resonant transformer of the generator presents a large leakage inductance that, without the addition of a resonating capacitance, would result in an output current of the generator that would be very low. In addition, a magnetic shunt in the transformer's core allows its operation even in short circuit. At the output of the generator, voltage and current are measured as described in section II.D.

C. Particle Image Velocimetry

The fluid flow field is visualized using particle image velocimetry (PIV). The PIV setup used is a 2-Dimensional 2-Component (2D-2C) commercial PIV system, by LaVision, which uses a single camera to measure the components of the fluid velocity field within a laser-light sheet. The wind tunnel ingests submicron droplets of mineral oil (DEHS) which are illuminated by two consecutive 532nm laser pulses of $2 \times 70\text{mJ/pulse}$ at close to 15Hz rate, triggered by an Nd:YAG dual cavity pulsed laser (Quantel Evergreen PIV 70). The timing between the consecutive pulses is selected based on the air speed that is being measured. For example, for a 2m/s wind speed a timing of $250\mu\text{s}$ is typically used, which allows the droplets to travel $500\mu\text{m}$ (equivalent to around 5.5 camera pixels) for 2D velocity-vector measurements. The laser head is fitted with sheet-forming optics that transform the laser beam into a laser sheet positioned 18.5cm from the top acrylic panel. Cylindrical lenses with 10mm focal length are used for this, and the mount allows adjusting the sheet waist focal length. The camera capturing the PIV frames is positioned at 68cm from the side acrylic panel and is a CX 12 imager fitted with an AF-S NIKKOR 18-55mm lens (Nikon DX) and a 532nm bandpass filter. This camera uses two frames per data point acquired, to individually capture each of the two consecutive laser pulses. The spatial resolution of the images is $90.9\mu\text{m/pixel}$. The gate of the camera for the first frame can be selected and is typically chosen to be $150\mu\text{s}$. The gate of the camera for the second frame is limited by the data acquisition and saving process and is automatically set at $\sim 26\text{ms}$. The laser sheet is positioned in the plane containing the dominant velocity vector (streamwise direction) and the vertical direction and is aligned to capture most of the airfoil chord length, see Fig. 2. In the chord direction, the laser sheet is offset from the strip-electrode center by 1cm (5mm from the edge), to avoid reflections of the laser on the metal sheet and facilitate resolving the flow field up until the airfoil surface.

Fig. 2 Photograph of representative experiment showing the DC arc advected by the wind, and the superimposed green laser sheet illuminating the PIV-tracer particles. Note that, close to the arc column and along its length, there is a region not illuminated by the laser sheet. This corresponds to the mineral oil droplets being evaporated by the arc heating and therefore resulting in a region void of tracers.

The timing of laser and camera is controlled by a programmable timing unit (PTU-X) provided by LaVision. PIV images are post-processed using the software DaVis 10.

D. Other Diagnostics Used and Synchronization

A second camera is placed side by side with the PIV camera detector, mounted on the same frame. This high-speed camera is used to track the dynamics of the arc column and to time-resolve the arc root motion. The high-speed camera is an Edgertronic SC2+ camera fitted with a 20mm Nikon lens fitted with a neutral density filter N8 (it transmits 12.5% of the broadband luminosity of the arc to avoid overexposure of the camera). The gate of the camera is typically selected at $1.25\mu\text{s}$ and the repetition rate at 3400fps. The spatial resolution of the images is 0.57mm/pixel . The high-speed camera is temporally synchronized to the electrode actuation system and the PIV elements (laser and camera) using the PTU-X box. Spatial calibration of the two cameras is done by taking an image of a calibration plate in order to align the origin and reference axes for the images taken by the different sensors.

The electrical signals (current and voltage) were measured via a DC/AC Hall effect current clamp, Fluke i30s, and two identical high voltage probes, model Fluke-80k-6, placed at the output of the high voltage generator (Fig. 1). The difference between these two voltage measurements gives the voltage drop along the arc. The electrical signals are recorded by a PicoScope model 3424 oscilloscope.

Measures were put in place to minimize EMI disturbances to the more sensitive equipment when the arc is triggered. These included an electrical isolation transformer for the PIV-subsystems, wrapping of electrical cables with metal jackets, placing electronics in metal boxes, using optic isolators between the PTU and the oscilloscope, grounding strip, and physical separation of the different subsystems.

III. RESULTS

Experiments were conducted at a range of wind speeds and airfoil angles of attack, for two separate electrode configurations: (i) upper ball electrode, and (ii) upper ball +

rail electrode. The first configuration tends to constrain the upper arc root and lock it in place. The second configuration allows for the free motion of the upper arc root along the rail. The polarity of the voltage applied to each of the electrodes is also explored to consider an anode-airfoil and a cathode-airfoil. The experimental matrix tested is summarized in Table I. For each of the configurations considered, at least 5 tests are recorded, as well as a baseline PIV dataset to have the raw flow velocity field in the absence of the arc. This amounts to over 200 cases to be analyzed.

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL TEST MATRIX

Upper Electrode: Ball or Rail		
Wind Speed [m/s]	Angle of Attack [deg]	Polarity Airfoil
1, 2, 4	0, 10, 20	Positive, Negative

The data acquired includes 2D measurement of the velocity fields, electrical waveforms, and arc column and arc root dynamics from the high-speed video. The high-speed video is post-processed to get quantitative information of the time-resolved evolution of the arc root position, the arc length, and the total luminosity of the arc. A sample image of the post-processing of the videos is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Image showing post-processing and analysis of high-speed videos. Airfoil is marked in green. Arc root motion as a function of time (time as a parameter) is marked in magenta. Instantaneous position of arc is shown in green (arc skeleton), visible region of the arc is marked in red. Image insert shows the arc length and total luminosity (uncalibrated) as a function of the camera frame. Case shown corresponds to that analyzed in section III.A: anode sample at zero AOA and 2m/s.

In what follows some representative results are summarized for the ball-upper electrode case and using 2m/s wind, for variable angle of attack and airfoil set to different polarities.

A. Anode Sample at Zero Angle of Attack

Fig. 4 shows a PIV image corresponding to the arc root in a position mid-way on the airfoil, for zero angle of attack and the airfoil as anode. The corresponding high speed video reveals that the anodic root *skips* (*small jumps*) along the airfoil, as it is being advected by the wind, while the upper root remains attached to the upper ball electrode. Fig. 3 shows the arc root tracking motion (in magenta) with time as a

parameter for this same case. The arc root skips can be clearly appreciated.

Fig. 4 Experimentally measured fluid velocity field overlaid with arc image for anodic airfoil, 2m/s and 0 degrees angle of attack.

Quantitative analysis of the high-speed videos, Fig.3, shows that the arc root skips by 5.7-6.8mm every ~ 5.5 -6ms, which corresponds to a root speed of 0.9-1.2m/s, as the root is in the boundary layer and experiences an overall speed lower than the 2m/s of the free stream.

The electrical waveforms (current and voltage drop across the arc) for case A are pictured in Fig. 5. The power supply is powered with the upper electrode in its uppermost position, at which point the voltage reading across the electrodes is the output of the power supply in open circuit: 4kV DC and no current flow. As soon as the upper electrode makes contact with the lower ball electrode, the power supply is short circuited, no voltage reading is measured (0kV DC) and there is a current flow. From about 0ms to 160ms, the electrodes are short-circuited, and around 160ms the upper electrode is retracted, increasing the arc length through a combination of the vertical electrode motion and the wind advecting the arc channel. Initially the arc is triggered between the two ball electrodes and the arc root jumps from the lower ball electrode to the airfoil electrode at about 215ms. From there the arc length increases as affected by the airflow alone, the voltage across the electrodes continues to increase, consistent with a fairly constant internal electric field. The current during this time is fairly steady at about 3A level. The arc extinguishes at about 430ms, when the current drops to zero and the voltage returns to an rms value of around 4kV.

The length of the arc channel is measured from the high-speed videos and is shown in Fig. 5 (in yellow). The arc length increases as the voltage increases, as the internal electrical field must remain approximately constant at constant current [7]. The evenly-spaced large spikes in the arc-length variable correspond to the laser pulses contaminating the measurements at that time-stamp (note they occur at the laser frequency of ~ 15 Hz). From the voltage and length, an internal electric field of the arc of ~ 28.8 V/cm is estimated (a voltage

drop of 1.24kV over 43cm length). This is comparable to that measured by King [7], who measured around $\sim 20\text{-}30\text{V/cm}$ for a 3A arc.

Fig. 5 Voltage drop across arc and current flow for anodic airfoil, 2m/s and 0 degrees angle of attack. Arc length as measured from high-speed camera footage. Relevant events are marked by text.

B. Cathode Sample at Zero Angle of Attack

Fig. 6 considers the same baseline fluid velocity field (zero angle of attack, 2m/s) but flipped polarity: the airfoil is the cathode. In this case, the cathodic arc root wants to stay *anchored* close to the airfoil leading edge and only undergoes a *big jump* before the arc extinguishes. This jump is measured to be (from the high-speed videos) around 16.5mm. As the arc elongates, this translates to a much longer section of the arc wrapped around the airfoil surface.

Fig. 6 Experimentally measured fluid velocity field overlaid with arc image for cathodic airfoil, 2m/s and 0 degrees angle of attack.

The electrical waveforms for case B are pictured in Fig. 7. The behavior is very similar for the anodic and cathodic cases, but the cathodic case shows a slightly faster rate of arc column growth. This can be appreciated by the steeper slope of the voltage drop between the arc root jumping from lower ball to airfoil, shortly after 250ms, and the arc extinguishing at around 415ms. The longer length of the arc is justified by the arc root staying in place instead of skipping. Another feature that is appreciated in Fig. 7 is that the arc root jumps at around 412ms, signaled by a sudden voltage drop, shortly before it extinguishes. This is seen in the high-speed footage as well. The arc length again is shown to increase in synchronization

with the voltage increase. Indeed, a longer length is achieved than for the anodic case, by about $\sim 8\text{cm}$ as a result of the arc root staying in place for most of the current flow phase. The internal electric field can again be estimated to be $\sim 32\text{V/cm}$.

Fig. 7 Voltage drop across arc and current flow for cathodic airfoil, 2m/s and 0 degrees angle of attack. Arc length as measured from high-speed camera footage. Relevant events are marked by text.

C. Anode Sample at 20 Degrees Angle of Attack

For cases A and B, the low wind speeds combined with the zero angle of attack led to a well-behaved flow field corresponding to laminar flow adhered to the airfoil. At high angles of attack, the flow can separate leading to a low velocity, highly turbulent region after the flow separation point that will affect the arc root dynamics. The next two cases explore the influence of having a separated flow on the arc column and arc root dynamics.

Fig. 8 shows the velocity field, with arc superimposed, for a case where the airfoil is the anode, the incoming flow is still at 2m/s, but the airfoil is pitching at a 20 degree angle of attack. Compared to the anode root skipping observed at zero angle of attack, in this case the arc root stays in place at the flow separation point and the arc column follows the separation of the flow.

Fig. 8 Experimentally measured fluid velocity field overlaid with arc image for anodic airfoil, 2m/s and 20 degrees angle of attack.

Fig. 9 shows the electrical waveforms for this case. Whereas the overall behavior is similar to the corresponding case with zero angle of attack (Fig. 5), the

main difference is that the case with 20 degrees angle of attack shows a slightly faster rate of arc column growth. This can be appreciated by the steeper slope of the voltage drop between the arc root jumping from lower ball to airfoil and the arc extinguishing. As before, the longer length of the arc is justified by the arc root staying in place instead of skipping. In this case, the arc root stays in place constrained by the fluid dynamics (separation of the flow). The arc length reaches $\sim 0.78\text{m}$ compared to the zero angle of attack anodic case, which peaks at $\sim 0.72\text{m}$.

Fig. 9 Voltage drop across arc and current flow for anodic airfoil, 2m/s and 20 degrees angle of attack. Arc length as measured from high-speed camera footage. Relevant events are marked by text.

D. Cathode Sample at 20 Degrees Angle of Attack

The following case considers the same high angle of attack condition but switching the polarity of the electrodes so that the airfoil is the cathode. In this case the results are similar to case C as the arc column and root dynamics are strongly constrained by the velocity field. Fig. 10 shows the velocity field superimposed to the arc image and the arc is seen to be sitting at the separation zone of the flow, as in Fig. 8.

Fig. 10 Experimentally measured fluid velocity field overlaid with arc image for cathodic airfoil, 2m/s and 20 degrees angle of attack.

Fig. 11 shows the electrical waveforms for this case which do not show much difference with respect to the case with zero angle of attack (Fig. 7), as in both cases the arc root does not move during the majority of the current flow. The slope of the voltage increase, as affected by the wind, is pretty much unchanged, indicating similar elongation of the arc in

both cases, as the ‘effective’ flow field is similar since the arc can not wrap around the airfoil as it did for the zero AoA case (because it follows the close to horizontal separation streamlines). The arc length peaks at $\sim 0.78\text{m}$ which is comparable to the zero angle of attack cathodic case at $\sim 0.8\text{m}$.

Fig. 11 Voltage drop across arc and current flow for cathodic airfoil, 2m/s and 20 degrees angle of attack. Arc length as measured from high-speed camera footage. Relevant events are marked by text.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Influence of flow velocity field

As in prior work, these results show different behavior of the arc root (whether skipping, sweeping, anchored in place, or jumping) depending on whether we are dealing with an anode or a cathode. One of the main findings is the strong influence of the flow velocity field. This has been demonstrated by characterizing *both* the fluid flow and the arc root motion and shows that flow separation strongly constrains the motion of both the arc column and the arc root. If the flow undergoes separation, the arc root is locked at the separation point as, downstream of that location, a low velocity recirculation region is encountered that the arc cannot penetrate. In these situations, the arc column sits at the separation region of the flow as it is advected above this zone. This happens regardless of the arc root being anodic or cathodic. The results show that indeed the arc column gets advected by the flow, but the behavior of the arc root is constrained by the local electrode physics.

B. Physical properties of the arc channel

It is interesting to compare the results obtained in this work, at low current levels and low wind speeds, to the results presented in [5] featuring wind tunnel experiments considering wind speeds between 40 and 60m/s, and DC electric arcs with currents from 200 to 600A, for similar arc lengths. Considering the arc channel hydrodynamic behaviour, for a zero degree AoA and a 2m/s wind, the arc voltage increase during the swept-stroke, e.g., the phase between the arc root jumping from the lower ball to the airfoil and the arc extinction, has a mean slope of around 11 V/ms for an anodic arc root and of around 19V/ms for a cathodic arc root (according to Figs. 5 and 7). For a wind speed of 60m/s, the work in [5] shows mean arc voltage slopes of around 280, 220 and 140V/ms for DC arcs of respectively 200, 400 and 600A, with comparable values for anodic and cathodic configurations. As it is difficult to determine and isolate the influence of the arc current intensity on the arc spatial

extension, the observed difference of arc voltage slopes - and by extension of arc length elongation - of an order of magnitude can be linked to first order to the difference in wind speed between the two configurations, of 2m/s and 60m/s. It is also interesting to note that the sample polarity slightly influences the arc voltage slope during the swept-stroke in the current experiments, as a result of the different arc root motions, whereas it is negligible in the experiments reported in [5]. Indeed, in the present work, the cathodic arc root tends to remain at its first attachment location on the airfoil for most of the swept-stroke phase, which allows the arc column to elongate more significantly, whereas in [5] the cathodic arc root tends to either glide or jump on the airfoil, following the arc column and thus reducing its elongation.

C. Arc Root Dynamics

The results of the arc root dynamics can also be compared with those presented in [4]. While a similar jumping mode of displacement on the airfoil has been observed in both our experiments and the experiments reported in [4], which involved higher currents and faster wind flows, our experiments depict a stalled cathodic arc root at 0° AoA. In contrast, the cathodic arc root exhibits continuous or semi-continuous motion on the airfoil under higher currents and faster wind flows. A possible explanation for this difference is related to the electronic emission mechanisms involved in forming a cathodic arc root: a cathodic spot has to emit electrons and receive positive ions to maintain the arc current. This emission is possible mainly through thermionic and field emission processes [8, 9]. In our electric arcs, it is possible that the arc current is not strong enough to sufficiently heat the airfoil surface surrounding the arc root to produce ionized metal, which would locally enhance the electric field. This lack of ionized metal would prevent the formation of close emitting spots that facilitate the motion of the arc root at a macroscopic scale as described in [4].

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented novel experimental results exploring the influence of different flow velocity fields on the dynamics of the arc column and the arc root behavior for long arcs of a few 10s of cm and 3A, exposed to 2m/s cross flows. Flow field characterization using Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) is presented for the first time in the presence of simulated lightning arcs. The presence of flow separation strongly influences the dynamics of both the arc column and

the arc root. Differences between anodic and cathodic behavior were observed with resemblance to results of experiments at higher currents and wind speeds. Future work will analyze the large set of data gathered during this wind tunnel campaign.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. A. Plumer, "Laboratory test results and natural lightning strike effects: how well do they compare," in *International Conference on Lightning Protection ICLP*, 31st:1-17, 2012.
- [2] D. W. Clifford and L. E. McCrary, "Final report: simulated lightning test Shuttle .03 scale model," *NASA Report MDC A3155*, 1974.
- [3] J. A. Dobbins and A. W. Hanson, "A swept stroke experiment with a rocket sled," in *IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, pages 390-395, 1978.
- [4] V. Andraud, R. S. Martins, C. Zaepffel, R. Landfried, P. Testé, and P. Lalande, "Arc root dynamics in the context of lightning strikes to aircraft," in *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* 57 (17), 175204, 2024.
- [5] V. Andraud, R. S. Martins, C. Zaepffel, R. Landfried, P. Testé, and P. Lalande, "Physical properties of the swept arc channel in the context of lightning strikes to aircraft," in *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* 56 (39), 395202, 2023.
- [6] C. Guerra-Garcia, N. C. Nguyen, J. Péraire, and M. Martinez-Sanchez, "Arc reattachment driven by a turbulent boundary layer: implications for the sweeping of lightning arcs along aircraft," in *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 49 (37), 375204 (14pp), 2016.
- [7] L. A. King, "The voltage gradient of the free burning arc in air and nitrogen," *Fifth International Conference on Ionization Phenomena in Gases*, vol. 2, pp. 871-877, 1961.
- [8] Murphy E L and Good Jr R H 1956 *Physical review* 102 1464.
- [9] Fowler R H and Nordheim L 1928 *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character* 119, 173-181.